

Recommended citation: De La Hoz, J. L., & Vieira, C. (2020). Promoting Metacognition Skills in Statics Through Self-Explanation: A Preliminary Study. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 1245-1251). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14654265](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14654265).

PROMOTING METACOGNITION SKILLS IN STATICS THROUGH SELF-EXPLANATION: A PRELIMINARY STUDY

De La Hoz, Jose Luis; Vieira, Camilo

Universidad del Norte
Barranquilla, Colombia

Conference Key Areas: *Future engineering skills and talent management, Engineering in Schools, Physics in the engineering curriculum.*

Keywords: *Statics; Metacognition; Self-Explanation, Problem-solving, Worked-Example*

ABSTRACT

This study explores how the use of self-explanation activities in Statics may support student development of metacognition skills. Metacognition can help students in Statics to be more aware of their thinking process for problem-solving. Self-explaining is a knowledge-building activity which may promote student metacognitive skills. This initial study explored the characteristics of student self-explanations of a given worked-example in the context of Statics equilibrium. Three students with different academic performances participated in an activity where they wrote their self-explanations for each step in the worked-example. The preliminary results demonstrate that students used different approaches to self-explain the worked-example, some approaches including instances of metacognitive processes, and how such differences may be related to their academic performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Statics is considered a fundamental engineering course that is difficult to understand for students. This particularity tends to have a negative impact on their performance in this subject and, therefore, in later courses which build on the proper understanding of Statics [1-3]. Promoting the development of students' cognitive and metacognitive skills can strengthen their problem-solving skills, and allow students to reason better about the physics and geometry concepts presented in the classroom. The goal of this research process is to explore the characteristics of student self-explanations of a given worked-example, and the relationship between students' approaches to self-explain and their problem-solving skills in the context of Statics equilibrium. Investigations suggest that there is a connection between students' prior knowledge and the kind of explanations they write [4].

This paper is organized as follows: (i) Section 2 explores the relationship between metacognition, self-regulation, and self-explanation activities; (ii) in Section 3 we describe the methodology concerning this investigation; (iii) Section 4 presents the results of this preliminary study, and (iv) the last section shows the conclusion and future work.

2 METACOGNITION, SELF-REGULATION, PHYSICS MISCONCEPTIONS AND SELF-EXPLANATIONS

Emphasizing the importance of controlling and regulating our own learning process is one of the tasks that educational researchers have long suggested in different areas of knowledge. Student academic performance could be considerably improved if they learn to regulate their learning process [5]. Metacognition refers to the knowledge we build regarding our cognitive processes and products, and the way in which we constantly monitor, control and organize these processes to achieve a desired end [6]. Cognitive regulation, also called self-regulation, is the metacognitive skill that allows students to regulate their learning process, managing the resources and strategies available to guarantee the success of a given task [7-8]. Teaching students to learn how to monitor their understanding may be helpful for developing their problem solving skills [9].

Self-explaining is a knowledge-building activity directed by the students who generate explanations for themselves. Students start from a worked-example and expert's solution to a problem – and should go beyond the provided information to create these explanations [13]. The self-explanations support student learning by: (1) the students identify and complete gaps in their understanding and missing information within the example; and (2) the students revise and repair their mental models by contrasting new information to what they already know [13]. The self-explanation activities demand students to be more aware of their learning process by monitoring their understanding of the worked-example. Monitoring the learning process itself is considered a metacognitive skill among those necessary for the students to self-regulate their learning [14]. This preliminary study explores the characteristics of student self-explanations of worked-examples in the context of Statics equilibrium, and the relationship of students' explanations and their performance in the course.

Student misconceptions about Physics affect student performance in Statics. These misconceptions are often represented in mistakes such as not considering all the forces between bodies in contact, not separating the system under study into sections, trigonometry mistakes, spatial perception and Newton's 3th law [10-12]. Hence, we may find some of these misconceptions in student self-explanations of Statics examples.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Design, Participants and Data collection

This study used a multiple case-study crossover design [15]. Three students enrolled in a Statics course at a private mid-size university were invited to participate in this study. These students obtained different academic performance during the course (Student A: High, Student B: Medium; Student C: Low). The data included students' written self-explanation of a worked-example of Statics equilibrium, which was divided into five steps following the Statics problem-solving model [16]. Figure 1 depicts two of the problem-solving steps in the worked-example. The unit of analysis

is each student individually. Due to space constraints the complete worked-example is not presented in this paper.

Student explanations were analysed using thematic analysis, a method employed to identify, analyse and report themes within collected information [17]. Every case was divided into categories, which were then classified in themes that would characterize the different approaches in students' self-explanations. For instance, one of the characteristics that are often present in a high-quality explanation includes the appropriate use of principles or laws and the proper application of conceptual knowledge [18-19]. The student explanations that connected to Statics principles and included a detailed explanation of the example were categorized as fine-grained explanations (FN).

<p>2. Modeling 2.1 To calculate stress "T" in each arm, it is necessary to understand that in order to stay fixed in the indicated position, the weight of the gymnast has to be compensated by the stresses of the ropes that hold the rings. From the free-body diagram on the right side, we calculate the vertical components of the stress "T" in each arm.</p>		<p>3. Governing equations: By symmetry, the magnitude of the stresses for both arms is equal. The rectangular component "Ty" is obtained by multiplying the stress "T" with the cosine of the angle formed with the adjacent leg.</p> $\sum F_y = 2T \cdot \cos\theta - mg = 0$
---	--	---

Fig.1. Fragments of worked-example activity: Step 2 (Modelling) describes how to find one of the unknowns by explaining what happens and its effects on the solution. Step 3 (Governing Equations) shows to the student how and why equations are structured for computing results.

Another important characteristic of high-quality explanations is the use of inferences [20-21]. These inferences (IN) are the result of students using background knowledge and clues from the example to fill the gaps in the information provided in the worked-example. To identify student metacognitive skills, we used categories such as planning (PL) and monitoring (MN). Planning statements are often used to identify the conditions under which certain procedures can be useful, while monitoring statements let them assess their understanding of the example. Also, if a student writes an own solution (OW) to a worked-example step, this is also considered an instance of a metacognitive process.

In addition to the self-explanation activity, students engaged in problem solving before and after the activity. Their responses to these problem solving activities were also qualitatively analysed. The categories derived from such process allow us to identify whether they included: effective use of trigonometric functions (TF), drawing free body diagram (FBD), and the right elaboration of equilibrium equations (EE).

4 RESULTS

Student C's self-explanation represents what we considered a poor quality self-explanation. Table 1 shows some Student C's explanations. Student C used a *limited approach* to self-explain the worked-example. Which means a poor quality

self-explanation that includes incorrect and incomplete explanations, paraphrasing and omitting valuable information from the example text. Common factors through his self-explanation.

Table 1. Extract of Student C’s self-explanation, their comparison against worked example text and characteristics

Student C’s sentences	Worked example text	Characteristic
<i>“...We will take into account tensions in arms are similar to be under the same conditions...”</i>	There is symmetry in the body (previously assumed), that is, the right side is subjected to the same conditions as the left side.	Paraphrasing
<i>“As described in point 1.”</i>	“...Subsequently, it will be necessary to know the angle of the resulting ‘R’ given by the weight of the body, in order to calculate the resulting force acting on the shoulder...”	Omitting valuable information

Student B was enrolled in the course for a second time and got better grades than Student C did. This student demonstrated understanding of the domain knowledge in Statics, going beyond the information provided (IN). Student B used her background knowledge or principles to describe each section. Table 2 shows an example of Student B’s explanation. Student B provided a higher quality self-explanation compared to Student C.

Table 2. Extract of Student B’s self-explanation and their characteristics

Student B’s sentence	Characteristics
<i>“Mainly, exercise poses a gymnast in balance whereby we can use the equations that always have been used $\sum F_x = 0$, $\sum F_y = 0$...In order to calculate stresses, which undoubtedly must have the same magnitude and enlargement angle, since they’re in the same conditions...”</i>	Background knowledge
	Mentioned a fundamental principle of Statics equilibrium
	More detailed explanation

Finally, Student A, who showed a high academic performance, demonstrated some instances of metacognitive skills in her explanations. A high-quality self-explanation depicts a clear conceptual understanding of the example and the ability to apply it in a different context (Transfer) [5]. Table 3 shows some parts from Student A’s explanation and their categories we assigned to it.

Table 3. Extract of Student A’s self-explanation and their characteristics

Student A’s sentences	Characteristics
“...The sum of the ‘Y’ components of both stresses are equal to the weight, and for static equilibrium we separate it and we get the stress...”	Planning
“...Since the arm is embedded in the shoulder there will be an “X, Y” reaction plus a Moment...”	Inference
“...The length of the arm is useless because there isn’t sum of Moments...”	Monitoring

Student A described the plan (PL) to calculate the unknowns. Also, the inferences made by her let us identify metacognitive skills inside of her written work. This student inferred (IN) a particular condition called embedded beam and its effects. Additionally, a monitoring statement (MN) were evidenced when she pointed out a given data point that was unnecessary.

As we just described, three students with different performances in Statics used different approaches to self-explain a given worked-example. Table 4 compares the differences in students’ approaches to self-explain. Evidently, academic performance plays an important role in the quality of student self-explanations

Table 1. Comparative chart.

Student (performance)	Quality Self-Explanations		Metacognition Skills			Concepts		
	FN	IN	PL	MN	OW	Math TF	Statics FBD	EE
A (high)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B (mid)	+	+	+	+
C (low)	+

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This preliminary study showed the different approaches students used to self-explain a worked-example, and how academic performance may be related to the quality of their explanations. These results are supported by previous research, which demonstrates that students with better academic performance go beyond to the given information [9], monitor their understanding [22] and write a greater number of self-explanations [23]. There are two main limitations for this study: the sample size (only three students) and a completed worked-example. Using incomplete or incorrect worked-examples may prompt student metacognitive processes to either complete or correct the problem solving process. Future work will compare the use of incomplete and incorrect worked-examples on the development of student metacognitive skills in a classroom environment.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] Streveler R, Geist M, Ammerman R, Sulzbach C, Miller R, Olds B, Nelson M, (2006). Identifying and Investigating Difficult Concepts in Engineering Mechanics and Electric Circuits, Proc. of the Annual Conference & Exposition, Chicago, Illinois, pp. 11.713.1-11.713.13.
- [2] Montfort D, Brown S, Pollock D, (2009). An Investigation of Students' Conceptual Understanding in Related Sophomore to Graduate - Level Engineering and Mechanics Courses, Journal of Engineering Education, Vol. 98, No. 2, pp. 111-129.
- [3] Haron N, Shaharoun A, (2010). Self-Regulated Learning, Students' Understanding and Performance in Engineering Statics. Proc. of the conference Learning Environments and Ecosystems in Engineering Education, Amman, Jordan, pp. 450-459.
- [4] Vieira C, Magana A, Roy A, Falk, M, (2019). Student Explanations in the Context of Computational Science and Engineering Education, Cognition and Instruction, pp. 1-31.
- [5] Bransford J, Brown A, Cocking R, (2000). How People Learn: Brain, Mind, Experience, and School: Expanded Edition, The National Academies Press, Washington, DC, pp. 24-51.
- [6] Flavell J, (1976). Metacognitive aspects of problem solving, The nature of intelligence, pp. 231-235.
- [7] Hartman H. (2001). Metacognition in Learning and Instruction: Theory, Research and Practice, Springer Netherlands, New York, pp. 19-32.
- [8] Zimmerman B, (1989). A Social Cognitive View of Self-Regulated Academic Learning, Journal of Educational Psychology, Vol. 81, No. 3, pp. 329-339.
- [9] Chi M, Bassok M, (1988). Learning from examples via self-explanations, Knowing, learning, and instruction: Essays in honor of Robert Glaser, pp. 251-282.
- [10] Gross P, Dinehart D, (2012). Identification of Common Student Errors In Solving Fundamental Mechanics Problems. American Society for Engineering Education.
- [11] Streveler R, Geist M, Ammerman R, Sulzbach C, Miller R, Olds B, (2006). Identifying and Investigating Difficult Concepts in Engineering Mechanics and Electric Circuits in American Society for Engineering Education.
- [12] Steif P, Dantzler J, (2005). Statics Concept Inventory: Development and Psychometric Analysis. Journal of Engineering Education, 363-371.
- [13] Chi M, (2000). Self-explaining expository texts: The dual processes of generating inferences and repairing mental models, Advances in instructional psychology, pp. 161-238.
- [14] Brown A, Bransford J, Ferrara R, Campione J, (1983). Learning, remembering and understanding, Handbook of child psychology, Vol. 3, New York, pp. 77-166.

- [15] Yin R, (2009). Case study research: Design and methods (4th Ed.), Sage, Thousand Oaks.
- [16] Gray G, Costanzo F, Plesha M, (2005). Problem solving in Statics and dynamics: A proposal for a structured approach. In 2005 ASEE Annual Conference and Exposition, Conference Proceedings. pp. 11543-11554
- [17] Braun V, Clarke V, (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology, *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 77–101.
- [18] Pirolli P, Recker M, (1994). Learning strategies and transfer in the domain of programming, *Cognition and Instruction*, Vol. 12, No. 3, pp. 235–275.
- [19] Sandoval W, Millwood K, (2005). The quality of students' use of evidence in written scientific explanations, *Cognition and Instruction*, Vol. 23, No. 1, pp. 23–55.
- [20] Renkl A, (1997). Learning from worked-out example: A study on individual differences, *Cognitive Science*, Vol. 21, No. 1, pp. 1–29.
- [21] Hidetsugu T, Nakatsu N, Hironari N, Neumann E, Shunichi M, (2007). Effects of self-explanation as a metacognitive strategy for solving mathematical word problems, *Japanese Psychological Research*, Vol. 49, pp. 222 - 233.
- [22] Roy M, Chi M, (2005). The self-explanation principle in multimedia learning, *The Cambridge handbook of multimedia learning*, Cambridge University Press, New York, pp. 271-286.
- [23] Litzinger T, Van Meter P, Firetto C, Passmore L, Masters C, Turns S, Zappe S, (2010). A Cognitive Study of Problem Solving in Statics, *Journal of Engineering Education*, pp. 337-353.